

**Velocity of Reaction in Mixed Solvents. Part I.
The Velocity of Reaction between Potassium Per-
sulphate and Potassium Iodide in Organic
Solvents-Water Mixtures.**

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Velocities of several chemical reactions in various solvents and mixtures of solvents have been found to be either accelerated or retarded. Cohen (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, **38**, 145) found that the hydrolysis of cane-sugar was retarded by the addition of alcohol to water. On the other hand, Walker and Kay (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, **71**, 480) found that the transformation of ammonium cyanate to carbamide in water was greatly accelerated by the addition of alcohol. Also Patterson and Forsyth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **401**, 40) found that methyl alcohol and acetone accelerated the reaction between iodic and sulphurous acids.

Bhonsen (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, **24**, 677) studied the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in mixed solvents and found that solvents exerted a specific effect on the velocity of reaction. Gosta Akerlof (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 1272) studied the decomposition of diacetone alcohol by sodium hydroxide, in water mixtures of organic solvents and found that in some of the pure alcohols the reaction velocity was largely influenced by traces of water, this influence decreasing with decreasing molecular weight of the alcohol or with increasing number of hydroxyl groups.

In view of the additive properties of mixtures, it is expected that the velocity of a reaction in mixed solvents will be intermediate between those in pure solvents and that the velocity constant-composition curves will be straight lines. Millar and Braune (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **85**, 1701) studied the decomposition of diazoacetic ester in alcohol-water mixtures and found a minimum in the

velocity constant-composition curve at 11 per cent. of water. Cashmore, McCombie, Scarborough and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 970; 1922, 121, 2421, 2301, 1229; 1923, 123, 2668.) studied the esterification of a number of esters in water-alcoholic mixtures and pointed out that the breaks in the velocity constant—composition curves occurred at such compositions of the solvents which in most cases are those demanded by simple complexes of alcohol and water.

In the present investigation the reaction between potassium persulphate and potassium iodide has been studied in mixtures of organic solvents and water. In aqueous solutions the kinetics of the reaction, which takes place as $K_2S_2O_8 + 2KI = 2K_2SO_4 + I_2$, was first studied by Price (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 27, 474) who using different methods for determining the order of a reaction, found the reaction to be of the second order. But Price had noticed that there was a slight divergence in experimental results calculated from the second order formula and these differences increased with the time for which the reaction was studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The velocity of the reaction has been studied in mixtures of water with methyl, ethyl and propyl alcohols, glycol, glycerol and pyridine.

Extra pure (Kahlbaum's) potassium persulphate was purified by crystallisation several times. The purity of the sample was determined by titrating the crystallised salt with ferrous sulphate. As potassium persulphate decomposes when exposed to light, it was kept in bottles wrapped in black paper.

Potassium iodide used was Merck's extra pure chemical and was found to be free from iodate.

All the organic solvents used were Merck's extra pure chemicals and were purified by the usual methods of dehydration and distillation.

Solutions of potassium persulphate and potassium iodide were made in water, redistilled from alkaline permanganate, fresh every time a reading was taken. The desired quantity of the organic solvents was added to one of the solutions and the two solutions were

placed in a thermostat maintained at 25°. When they had acquired the temperature of the bath, they were mixed and it was so arranged in all the experiments that the initial concentrations of potassium iodide and potassium persulphate in the mixture were $N/50$. The total volume of the reaction mixture was 100 c.c. but in experiments where higher percentages of the organic solvents were used, it was increased to 250 c. c.

Potassium persulphate is a great oxidising agent and consequently low concentrations of potassium persulphate were used to avoid or to minimise the oxidation of alcohols. Also the error caused by the interaction of the liberated iodine with the organic solvents would be very insignificant as the velocity of the above reaction is extremely slow. Ten or 25 c. c. of the reaction mixture were removed to conical flasks, containing ice-cold water, at different intervals and the amount of the liberated iodine was determined by titrating the mixture against $N/100$ -sodium thiosulphate solution. The reaction was usually allowed to proceed for two to three hours but in mixtures containing higher percentage of the organic solvents, it was continued for a longer time.

In calculating the results the initial concentration, a , of potassium iodide and persulphate and the amount of the liberated iodine, x , are expressed in terms of c. c. of $N/100$ -sodium thiosulphate required for 25 c. c. of the reaction mixture. As the concentrations of the reactants are equal, the velocity constant, k , has been calculated from the bimolecular formula,

$$k = 1/t. \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$$

The results obtained are given in the following tables. Every experiment was repeated three or four times and the values of x given in the tables are the mean of three or four readings.

TABLES I.

Solvent—water.

t	...	4	24	44	64	84	104	114
x	...	0.64	3.61	6.19	8.41	10.85	12.10	18.65
$k \times 10^3$	...	64	64	64	68	62	62	62
							Mean	68

TABLE II.

Mean values of $k \times 10^6$

Organic solvents.	0%	10%	20%	35%	50%
Methyl alcohol ...	63.0	41.0	29.0	15.0	10.4
Ethyl alcohol ...	..	40.0	26.0	17.0	15.5
Propyl alcohol ...	..	40.0	27.0	24.0	29.0
Glycol ...	..	45.7	33.8	18.1	—
Glycerol ...	..	57.0	53.0	47.0	39.0
Pyridine ...	..	7.6	3.7	1.6	1.0

The velocity constants have been plotted against the composition of the mixed solvents and the curves obtained are shown in Fig. 1. The percentage of the organic solvents higher than 50 could not be used due to the considerable decrease in the solubility of potassium persulphate in such mixtures.

Velocity constant—composition curves.
(Potassium persulphate-iodide)

(FIG. 1)

It will be seen from Table II that the addition of the organic solvents to water, retards the reaction between persulphate and the iodide ions in water; the retardation is greater with greater percentage of the organic solvents in the mixture. But propyl alcohol behaves slightly in a different manner. The velocity constant decreases with the increase in the propyl alcohol content of the mixture up to a certain concentration only; higher concentrations than this increase the velocity constants (*cf.* a minimum point in the curve A Fig. 1).

The velocity constant—composition curves in mixtures containing methyl, ethyl and propyl alcohols, cut each other below 35 per cent. content of the alcohols but in mixtures containing more than 35 per cent. of these substances, the retarding influence decreases in the following order:—

Increase of the hydroxyl groups in the molecule of the organic solvents also decreases the retarding effect.

Organic solvent.	Number of (OH) groups.	Percentage of the organic solvents.				
		10	20	35	50	
Methyl alcohol	...	1	41.0	39.0	15.0	10.4
Glycol	...	2	45.7	39.8	18.1	—
Glycerol	...	3	57.0	53.0	47.0	39.0

Potassium persulphate is fairly soluble in water but insoluble in alcohols. But the decrease in the velocity constant is not in any way due to the decrease in the solubility of potassium persulphate by the addition of the organic solvents as in all the experiments the amount of potassium persulphate used was much smaller than that required for the saturated solution of potassium persulphate in water at 25°. Also in no experiment any precipitation of the solutes was observed. There is also no decrease in the concentration of potassium persulphate due to the oxidation of the organic solvents by the persulphate. For in some experiments potassium persulphate was kept in contact with the alcohols for two hours before adding to the potassium iodide solution and the mean velocity constant obtained in such an experiment was the same as obtained by mixing the two solutions immediately.

Buchbock (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1897, 23, 123) has suggested that an increase in the viscosity of the solvent decreases the rate of reaction. But it will be seen from Table II that the velocity constants in glycerine-water and glycol-water mixtures are greater than alcohol-water and pyridine-water mixtures contrary to the above suggestion. Also the viscosities of the alcohol-water mixtures are maximum at certain compositions and therefore the velocity constants should be minimum at those concentrations. No minimum point has been observed in the present investigation in mixtures of methyl and ethyl alcohols ; a minimum point has only been observed in the case of propyl alcohol but not at the composition of the maximum viscosity. It appears probable that the viscosity of the medium does not exercise any appreciable influence on the rate of reaction. Bhonson (*loc. cit.*) has also come to similar conclusions.

The dielectric constants of organic solvents and of their mixtures with water are lower than that of water. Salzar (*Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1924, 22, 275) has found that the dielectric constant composition curves of the mixtures are straight lines and show discontinuities at compositions of certain hydrates of alcohols. The velocity constants of a reaction in pure organic solvents and in their mixtures with water will, according to Nernst-Thomson rule, be lower than in pure water. Although this has been found to be the case, yet the velocity constant—composition curves are not straight lines showing that there exists no direct proportionality between the velocity constants and the dielectric constants and that the dielectric constant is not the only factor influencing the rates of reaction.

Another important factor which exercises an influence on the velocity of the reaction is the molecular association of the solvents (*cf.* Cashmore, etc., *loc. cit.*). The minimum point observed in the case of propyl alcohol corresponds to the hydrate $C_3H_7OH \cdot 8H_2O$, the existence of which has already been shown by Christensen (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 257). It is possible therefore that alcohols producing the alcohol hydrates in the mobile state bring about a change in the regular behaviour of the mixtures at the particular composition.

It cannot therefore be said at present as to which is the deciding factor in controlling the velocity of a reaction in mixtures of organic solvents with water. Recently this reaction has been studied by Kiss and Hatz (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1929, 48, 7), in mixtures of methyl and ethyl alcohols and glycerol with water and they have also found

that the addition of these substances lowers the speed of the reaction and that no simple relation exists between the velocity constants and the concentration of the non-electrolytes. Also these workers could not find any relationship between the dielectric constants of the mixtures and the velocity constant of the reaction.

Summary.

1. The reaction between potassium persulphate and potassium iodide has been studied in water and in mixtures of water with methyl, ethyl, and propyl alcohols, glycol, glycerol and pyridine.

2. All the organic solvents retard the reaction: the retardation is greater as the concentration of these solvents in the mixture is increased.

3. A minimum point in the velocity constant—composition curve occurs in the case of propyl alcohol.

4. Increase of OH-groups decreases the retarding effect.

5. There is no relation between the velocity constant and the dielectric constants or the viscosities of the mixtures.

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